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The Role of Vedānta as a Mediator between Science and Religion

Dr. Abdulla Sha R.¹, Dr. Midhun P.,²

Abstract

The war between science and religion from ancient times is still going on with almost the same intensity. The cultural quality of a country can be deduced from the development of its philosophies. The prosperity of a nation is attributed to the physics that make external life comfortable. Some thinkers believe that the day when science defends God in a laboratory will be the last day that people need faith. It is being considered how Vedānta fulfills its duty to mediate this conflict of opinion between religion and science.

Introduction

Religion and science are, respectively, experiments on the truth, both manually and spiritually. They both try to find their own truths by going in parallel. The ultimate goal of both is the multifaceted development of human. While science — especially modern science — seeks to bring material pleasures to man on the material level, religion seeks to quench man's spiritual thirst.

But the war between science and religion from ancient times is still going on with almost the same intensity. In the great triumph of science, the question arises as to what is wrong in acknowledging that evil visions and the demand for evidence have become an enlightened thought, but that something beyond all our common sense is evolving. Vedānta philosophy, with all its relevance, goes to the point where some thinkers believe that the day when science

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defends God in a laboratory will be the last day that people need faith. Here it is being considered how Vedānta fulfills its duty to mediate this conflict of opinion between religion and science.

Indian Philosophy and Vedānta

The cultural quality of a country can be deduced from the development of its philosophies. The prosperity of a nation is attributed to the physics that make external life comfortable and the philosophies that make internal life satisfying. Despite its many political, racial and linguistic differences, what sets India apart from other countries is a culture that exists here (which requires a discussion to say 'still exists') that unites us all.

The philosophies we possess, are the result of moving away from the realm of physics and exploring the mysteries of the universe. Since it is based not only on logic but also on experience, the term 'Darśanam' is derived from the Sanskrit root 'Dṛśir' which means 'to see or observe in detail' ('दृशिर् प्रेक्षणे', घातु.1472) to describe philosophies. Since all the philosophies deal with and interpret theology in every way, there is no doubt that the last method, Vedānta philosophy, is the first consideration.

Religions and Vedānta

Dharma – in this context, religion - is the one that explains the purpose of life and helps man to attain material and spiritual enlightenment. Religion, which prescribes the path to healing, is inextricably linked with life. As human beings became different due to cultural differences, so did different religions. Although the costumes are different and the anatomy of man is the same, the rituals are different from country to country, but there are many similarities between the internal religious truths. Or, if there is no similarity, then it must be understood that the ultimate truth is not there. The doctrine of all doctrine, judged by human intellect and culture, is ultimately the same. Everyone is given the freedom to act on the advice they receive.

Practically speaking, Dvaita, Viśiṣṭādvaita and Advaita are the very philosophies of Vedānta itself. Dvaita, Viśiṣṭādvaita and Advaita are the three phases in the concept of God: Saṅuṇa-sākāra

(Having a form and features), Saguṇa-nirākāra (Having a form but no features) and Nirguṇa-nirākāra (Formless and featureless). For example, Christianity possessed Saguṇa-nirākāra, and Islam, Nirguṇa-nirākāra. Hinduism, on the other hand, has adopted these three expressions.

Saguṇa-sākāra (Dvaitam) is the imagination of temples, idols, virtues and forms. Saguṇa-sākāropāsānā or idolatry is practiced because it is difficult to meditate on something that has not been seen, heard or known. Even though the ground is full of water, the ubiquitous God enters the temples with more vigor, as if a well had to be dug to make it useful, and the milk spread all over the body of the cow can only be obtained by sucking the nipple.

Saguṇa-nirākāra (Viśiṣṭādvaita) is a concept that is immaterial but with qualities such as love and kindness. The concept of Nirguṇa-nirākāra is immortal and eternal because it is transcendental.

As a child, who is dependent on his parents for everything in his childhood, as he gets older, he will be able to think as a dualist as long as he has a physical imagination, as he begins with a dualistic imagination, turns into a dualistic dualism, and as the realm of empathy expands, he will feel the wonderful fruit of non-dualism.

One is a Dvaitin when he thinks himself the body and the servant of God. He is a Viśiṣṭādvaitin when one realizes himself as Jīva and the essence of God. Advaitin when one thinks himself as the same as God. It is as if the sky is really the same, even though it may look different in different points of views like Ghaṭākāśa and Paṭākāśa.

“देवभावे तु दासोऽहं जीवभावे त्वदंशकः ।

आत्मभावे त्वमेवाहम् इति मे निश्चिता मतिः ॥” (Sūktisudhākara)

This verse of Hanuman expresses the same idea. Jesus Christ preached “our heavenly Father” in two ways. “My Father is greater than me, and I am part of it,” he said. He is also an Advaitin when he says, ‘I and my Father are one.’ According to the paradigm, these three levels were approved by Christ.

Thus a Vedāntin adopts both the aspects of God - Saguṇa and Nirguṇa. Whether openly acknowledged or not, these theories have had a profound effect on many religions and creeds.

Science and Vedānta

If we ask whether the foundations of religion are being shaken in this great triumph of science, we must say no. One of the reasons for this, is that Vedānta philosophy is so close to science. There is nothing in Vedānta that is incompatible with science and logic.

Vedānta declares that this sensory universe originated from Praṇavam or Omkara. It is, in fact, an extension of what has happened, is happening, and will continue to happen. The rising Omkāra sound dissipated at its rapid pace. Those particles, which were disintegrated into many particles, together became five elements called Pañcabhutas. (The Bible also says that, in the beginning was the Word (Bible: Yoha: 1:1)). The mystery of the Big bang theory was documented long before science discovered it!

According to the mantra “कथमसतः संजायते”, nothing comes out of nothingness. In the sixteenth verse of the second chapter of the Bhagavad Gita, it is pointed out that there is no lack of essence and no reality of essence.

“नासतो विद्यते भावो नाभावो विद्यते सतः ।

उभयोरपि दृष्टोऽन्तस्त्वनयोस्तत्त्वदर्शिभिः ॥” (Bhagavadgita. 2.16)

This is, in fact, the Law of Conservation of Matter.

Inertia is the state between matter and antimatter. Both are energy. Gold and soil, although they may seem different, gold is energy and so is soil. Science theorizes that both are different forms of energy. The same is the theory of relativity of Albert Einstein, that, humans, animals, wood and soil have all expanded from energy.

Energy can be transformed but cannot be destroyed. When deformed, the sum of the energies before and after the change is equal. This is known as the Energy Conservation Act. This is the essence of all the laws of nature. This is also the Vedānta principle that the universe is ‘Vivarta’, the illusory transformation of Brahma.

Science can only accept the fact that everyone has the same experience wherever they look. It is this remarkable principle that inspired the theory of relativity. Relativity is a tendency that is inherent in our thinking without us knowing it. Nothing in the universe deviates from this law. All perceptions of being small, big,

beautiful and ugly are relative.

Conclusion

In the light of the above, many of the theories of the Siddhas who have explored the fundamentals of life are in line with science. Religion is not something that the brain can understand. It must be understood by the heart.

Buddha has said that each of us is a god. Each of us knows everything. We just have to open our minds to listen to our own wisdom. It has been acknowledged by many scientists that there is some order in all natural processes, that the universe does not work automatically, but under certain laws. From all this, it is clear that religion and science are not contradictory but complementary. If they work together, it will bring great benefits to the world with prosperity, happiness and peace.

References

- Tapasyananda, Swami, Bhakti Schools of Vedanta, Sri Ramakrishna Math, Madras, 2003
- Srinivasachari, P.N., The Philosophy of Viśiṣṭādvaita, The Adayar Library and Research Centre, Adayar, Madras, 1978
- Ranganathananda, Swami, Practical Vedanta and the Science of Values, Adwaitashrama, Calcutta, 1995
- Parthasarathy, A., Vedanta Treatise – The Eternities, A. Parthasarathy, Mumbai, 2009
- Mohan Roy, Raja Ram, Vedic Physics – Scientific Origin of Hinduism, Golden Egg Publishing, Toronto, 1999
- Jitatmananda, Swami, Modern Physics and Vedanta, Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Mumbai, 2006

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